

**PROSPECTS FOR THE ROLE OF TOURISM IN NATIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN
AZERBAIJAN: THE LANKARAN–ASTARA REGION****Tural Alakbarov***Assistant,**Azerbaijan Technological University***Ferman Isgenderov***Docent,**Azerbaijan Technological University***Fizuli Musayev***Lecturer,**Azerbaijan Technological University***Abstract**

This article investigates the role of tourism as a component of national economic development, specifically examining the southern regions of Azerbaijan. The primary objective of the research is to comprehensively analyze the tourism potential of the Lankaran-Astara economic region and identify its developmental prospects. The study indicates that the development of tourism positively impacts increasing employment, revitalizing the local economy, and improving infrastructure in the region. Simultaneously, existing challenges—such as infrastructure deficiencies, inconsistent service quality, and weak international promotion—have been identified, and proposals for addressing them have been put forward. Consequently, the development of tourism within the Lankaran-Astara economic region occupies a significant place in Azerbaijan's regional and national economic development strategy, and the sustainable growth of this sector holds substantial importance for future prospects.

Keywords: tourism, economic, development, regional, Lankaran–Astara economic region

Introduction. In the modern era, the tourism sector acts as a component of national economic development, playing a vital role in the socio-economic progress of nations. Particularly within the context of regional development, the role of tourism becomes increasingly relevant, as this field directly influences the efficient utilization of local resources, the increase of employment, and the development of infrastructure. From this perspective, studying the tourism potential of the regions in the Republic of Azerbaijan and involving them in economic turnover holds significant scientific and practical importance. The study presents tourism opportunities as a component of national economic development using the example of Azerbaijan's southern regions and investigates developmental prospects. Specifically, the Lankaran-Astara economic region was kept in focus due to its distinctive rich natural resources, favorable geographical position, and diversified tourism resources.

Located in southern Azerbaijan between the shores of the Caspian Sea and the Talysh Mountains, the Lankaran-Astara economic region possesses a favorable position from both natural and economic perspectives. The region's border with Iran and the passage of major international transport corridors through this area enhance its strategic importance. Historically established as a center of trade and culture, the city of Lankaran continues to serve as one of the region's primary tourism hubs today. (Schuhbert & Thees, 2020).

Research indicates that the region's tourism potential is multifaceted. This includes resort-recreational resources, national parks with rich biodiversity, mountain and waterfall landscapes, historical-cultural heritage sites, maritime tourism opportunities, as well as rural and agrotourism resources. Specifically, natural areas such as Hirkan National Park and Gizilagaj National Park increase the region's international significance in terms of ecotourism.

Simultaneously, unique natural sites such as Yanar Bulag (Burning Spring), mountain villages in Lerik and Yardimli, historical monuments like the Lankaran Fortress, and recreation zones located on the Caspian coast ensure the diversity of the region's tourism product. Furthermore, traditional agricultural sectors such as tea and citrus farming create conditions for the development of agrotourism, while local festivals and cultural events facilitate the formation of ethnotourism.

Thus, the study conducted on the example of the Lankaran–Astara economic region determines that the tourism sector, while playing a vital role in the socio-economic development of the region, functions as a component of national economic development. The efficient utilization of the region's existing tourism potential and the application of sustainable development strategies can further strengthen its position in both domestic and international tourism markets in the future.

At the same time, unique natural objects such as Yanar Bulaq, mountain villages of Lerik and Yardimli, historical monuments like the Lankaran Fortress, as well as recreation zones located on the Caspian coast, ensure the diversity of the region's tourism product. Furthermore, traditional agricultural sectors such as tea and citrus farming create conditions for the development of agrotourism, while local festivals and cultural events facilitate the formation of ethnotourism.

Thus, as a result of the research conducted on the example of the Lankaran–Astara economic region, it is determined that the tourism sector, while playing an important role in the socio-economic development of the region, also functions as a component of national economic development. The efficient utilization of the region's existing tourism potential and the application of sustainable development strategies can further strengthen its position in both the local and international tourism markets in the future.

Located in southern Azerbaijan, between the shores of the Caspian Sea and the foothills of the Talysh Mountains, the Lankaran-Astara economic region encompasses the administrative territories of Yardimli, Astara, Jalilabad, Lerik, Masalli, and Lankaran. Its position on the border with Iran and the passage of a major international transport route through this area grant the region strategic importance. As an ancient port city, Lankaran was historically surrounded by fortress walls and developed over many years as a trade center. The resort-recreational potential of the region is particularly noteworthy. The existence of nearly 20 mineral springs in the Astara district alone, along with the availability of therapeutic sea, sand, and sun baths in Lankaran, makes this area a significant destination for health tourism. Sanatoriums such as "Ibadi-Istisu" (Lankaran), "Istisu," "Gamo," and "Yanardag" (Masalli), as well as the "Meshabeyi" and "Relax" recreation complexes in Lerik, operate within the region. Təbii turizm ehtiyatları və milli parklar

One of the region's greatest advantages is its unique nature. In this regard:

Hirkan National Park – rich in rare relict and endemic plants, it encompasses the Hirkan forests included in the UNESCO list. It is favorable for ecotourism, trekking, and photo-tourism. Hirkan National Park is considered one of the most important natural assets of the region. This park was primarily established to protect Hirkan-type relict forests, where plant species dating back millions of years have been preserved to this day. Rare and endemic plants such as the ironwood (parrotia), chestnut-leaved oak, and Hirkan boxwood are widespread within the park's territory.

Furthermore, the area is distinguished by its rich fauna. Animals such as the Caucasian leopard, bear, lynx, and wild boar are found here. Hirkan National Park is highly conducive to ecotourism, facilitating activities such as trekking, scientific research tours, biodiversity studies, and photo-safaris. Its inclusion in the UNESCO World Heritage list further enhances the area's attractiveness for international tourism.

Gizilagaj National Park – one of the primary habitats for migratory birds, it holds special significance for ornithological tourism. Gizilagaj National Park is one of Azerbaijan's most important wetland ecosystems and is of great importance, particularly for ornithological tourism. This area is included in the Ramsar zone of international importance and serves as a wintering and nesting site for thousands of migratory birds.

Gizilagaj National Park creates extensive opportunities for ecological awareness, birdwatching, photography, and scientific research tourism. In this respect, it plays a vital role in diversifying the region's tourism product.

Yanar Bulag – is one of the rare natural phenomena where water ignites, serving as an intriguing attraction for tourists. Yanar Bulag is considered one of the most unique natural monuments in the region. The primary distinguishing characteristic of this spring is its ability to ignite due to the influence of natural gases contained within the water. When a flame is lit over the spring, the water continues to burn, representing a natural occurrence rarely encountered globally.

This phenomenon generates significant interest for tourists from both scientific and visual perspectives. Especially in terms of ecotourism and geotourism, Yanar Bulag possesses the potential to become a tourism brand for the region. Tourists visiting the area can observe these extraordinary features of nature while enjoying the natural beauty of the surrounding villages.

The conducted research indicates that the Lankaran-Astara economic region, possessing a rich and diversified tourism potential, plays a vital role as a component of national economic development. The region's favorable geographical position, its location on the shores of the Caspian Sea, and its enclosure by the Talysh Mountains create conditions for the parallel development of various types of tourism. (Guliyev & Nurdiyeva, 2017; Molan et al., 2021).

As a **result** of the research, it has been determined that the region's tourism resources are formed along the following directions:

- resort and health tourism (mineral springs, therapeutic climatic conditions)
- ecotourism and biodiversity (Hirkan National Park, Gizilagaj National Park)
- mountain and adventure tourism (territories of Lerik and Yardimli)
- historical-cultural tourism (Lankaran Fortress and other monuments)
- maritime tourism (Caspian shores)
- rural and agrotourism (tea farming, citrus farming, rural lifestyle)
- festival and ethnographic tourism

This diversity allows for the diversification of the tourism product in the region, the ensuring of year-round tourism activity, and the increase of economic revenues. Simultaneously, the tourism sector positively impacts the enhancement of employment, the development of infrastructure, and the improvement of the social welfare of local communities in the region.

However, during the study, it was identified that despite the existing potential, the development of the tourism sector in the region has not been fully realized. Infrastructure deficiencies, inconsistent service quality, weak international promotion, and limited investment opportunities restrict the development of this field to a certain extent.

Proposals. To utilize the region's tourism potential more efficiently and to strengthen its role as a component of national economic development, the implementation of the following measures is considered appropriate: modernization of road, transport, and communication systems, Increasing the number of hotels, recreation centers, and service facilities in the region, Improving accessibility for tourism in mountain and rural areas, expansion of ecological tourism routes within the territories of Hirkan National Park and Gizilagaj National Park, harmonization of tourism activities with the preservation of biodiversity, organization of ecological awareness programs, involvement of the local population in tourism activities, supporting guesthouses and rural tourism enterprises, parallel development of health, adventure, cultural, and festival

tourism directions promotion of unique sites such as Yanar Bulag as tourism brands.

References

1. Alakbarov, T. T., Gurbanova, A. R. and Musaeva, L. Sh. (2026) ‘The role of tourism in regional economic development: experience of the eastern regions of Azerbaijan’, *Vestnik nauki*, (3 (96)). Available at: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rol-turizma-v-regionalnom-ekonomicheskom-razviti-opyt-vos-tochnyh-regionov-azerbaydzhana> (Accessed: 21 March 2026). <https://doi.org/10.24412/2712-8849-2026-396-600-607>
2. Alakbarov, T. (2025) “Turizm və xarici iqtisadi əlaqələr” book. Azerbaijan Technological University. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/401621247_Turizm_v_xarici_iqtisadi_laqlr
3. Guliyev, S.M. and Nuriyeva, K. (2017) “ADVENTURE TOURISM MARKETING: A RESEARCH ON THE TOURISTS’ BEHAVIOURS REGARDING TO ADVENTURE TOURISM IN AZERBAIJAN,” *DergiPark* (Istanbul University) [Preprint]. Available at: <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/ijbms/article/405196> (Accessed: November 2025).
4. Molan, A.S. et al. (2021) “Border Tourism Development Strategies in Kaleybar Compared to Regional Rivals,” *Sustainability*, 13(20), p. 11400. doi:10.3390/su132011400.
5. Schuhbert, A. and Thees, H. (2020) “Of routes and corridors: Challenges and opportunities for Silk Road destinations in the southern Caucasus,” *Econstor* (Econstor) [Preprint]. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3835829.